

The six pyramids and planets at Giza

Scaling the heights.

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Abstract

In a previous paper, Zep Tepi Mathematics 101 [1], and the ones it references, I showed how Giza had six main pyramids, with a mathematically designed layout, based on a stellar arrangement around 55.5k BCE. One “problem” with that proposal is that the sizes of the pyramids do not match the brightness of the stars. In this paper I show that the pyramid sizes actually correlate to the sizes of the six planets closest to the sun, with the pyramids arranged from west to east in increasing size order. This implies that the builders could accurately measure the diameters of the five planets plus Earth, as well as being aware of the four Galilean moons, and Saturn’s moon, Titan. This implies they had optical instruments like telescopes.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, pyramids, archaeoastronomy, history of astronomy.

Best viewed and printed in colour.

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1. Introduction

“That which is above is from that which is below, and that which is below is from that which is above.”

The Emerald Tablet

“Look on my Works, ye Mighty, and despair!”

Ozymandias , Percy Bysshe Shelley

“You will believe.”

The architects of Giza

In Zep Tepi Mathematics 101 (ZTM101) [1] I showed the Giza site plan as in Fig. 1, based on double $1000\sqrt{5}$ royal cubits (\mathcal{C}) squares. See that paper for how to calculate the positions of the pyramids. This paper has frequent references to results from ZTM101, and I assume the reader is familiar with it.

Figure 1: The Giza site plan with six pyramids

This aligns with the stars around 55.5k BCE, as in Fig. 2:

Figure 2: How the stars inspired the design. The date is 55.5k BCE.

A critique of this alignment (apart from the problematic date), is the poor correlation between the brightness of the stars, and their associated pyramids. For example, Vega and Arcturus are two of the brightest stars in the heavens, yet they are matched to the two smallest pyramids.

Table 1 shows the correlation between the relative brightness of the stars, and the associated pyramids, with Arcturus set at 100%.

Star	Pyramid	Visible magnitude	Percent of Arcturus
Arcturus	P4 Centre	-0.05	100.0
Vega	P6 Centre	0.03	92.9
Alioth	P2 Centre	1.76	18.9
Alkaid	P3 Centre	1.85	17.4
Mizar	P2 SW	2.23	12.2
Merak	P1 Centre	2.34	11.1
Megrez	P2 NE	3.32	4.5
Thuban	P5 Orbital	3.67	3.3

Table 1: The stars, pyramids, visible magnitudes and relative brightness.

This is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Relative brightness of the stars, visually shown.

Expecting star brightness to match pyramid size is perhaps a modern conceit, and assumes that the builders thought the same way that we do, and did not have better reasons for allocating the pyramid sizes. It turns out that they did have better reasons, which are related to the planets rather than the stars. Before I explain, let us review the other attempts to marry the pyramids to the planets.

2. Other attempts at matching the planets to the pyramids

I found six other works looking at the planets at Giza. Typically, they align Khufu with Earth, Khafre with Venus, and then try to make Menkaure match to Mars, Mercury, or the moon. Menkaure is not a good match for any, on that scale.

The most well-known work is probably the one by Hans Jelitto, *Planetary Correlation of the Giza Pyramids – P4 Program Description*. [2]

This matches Earth, Venus, and Mercury orbital paths to the three pyramids, as well as Khufu's internal structures to the planetary orbits.

Douglas M. Keenan's book, 'Our Solar System in the Layout at Giza' [3] maps Earth, Venus, and Mars/Mercury, after developing a mathematical model.

The late researcher Clive Ross extends work done by the late M. Koder, and takes a different approach to the previous two authors. He constructs a triangle around the three pyramids, and then shows how the planets fit into this design.[4] [Note: his web page has an incorrect Title.]

Following on from Clive Ross, Don Barone produces some interesting planetary ratios using the pyramid dimensions, and favourite irrationals like π , ϕ , and $\sqrt{3}$. [4]

Researcher David Carr takes a completely different and original approach. He shows how one can map the differences in north-south and east-west distances between pyramid centres to produce a reasonably accurate model of the distances from the sun, for all four inner planets. [5]

I found this compelling.

French researcher Jean Seimple has a paper which brings Central American pyramids, and the supposed Planet X, into the equation. [6]

These authors were of course hampered by only having the three extant pyramids to work with, as well as the wrong size for Menkaure. I have six pyramids, and the correct size for Menkaure, so we can try a different approach.

3. Mapping the six planets to the pyramids

As with most of what I have found at Giza, this was a haphazard, stumbling discovery. In truth, I have been looking for a planetary connection since before I found the stellar connection, and was actually looking for the planets at that time. Eventually, the methodology became clear, and like other things, it is almost obvious once revealed.

The secret is this: **The equatorial diameters of the planets, relative to Jupiter, closely match the volumes of the pyramids, relative to Khufu.**

Or expressed more mathematically,

$$\text{Equatorial diameter} \left(\frac{\text{planet}}{\text{Jupiter}} \right) \approx \text{volume} \left(\frac{\text{pyramid}}{\text{Khufu}} \right)$$

We can not expect the correlation to be exact. We don't know what technology they had to measure the diameters of the planets. Also, there were other mathematical considerations for the sizes of the pyramids, over and above matching to the planets.

NASA supplies the planetary equatorial diameters as in Table 2: [7]

<i>Planet</i>	<i>Equatorial diameter km</i>	<i>Percentage of Jupiter</i>
Saturn	120536.0	84.30
Jupiter	142984.0	100.00
Mars	6792.4	4.75
Earth	12756.3	8.92
Venus	12103.6	8.47
Mercury	4881	3.41

Table 2: Planet diameters as a percentage of Jupiter.

The base and heights for the pyramids, as used in Zep Tepi Mathematics 101, are:

<i>Giza / stellar name</i>	<i>P number</i>	<i>Base X G</i>	<i>Base Y G</i>	<i>Height G</i>
Khufu	P1	440	440	280
Khafre	P2	411	411	274
Menkaure	P3	201	195	126
Arcturus	P4	149	151	100
North Pole / Thuban	P5	193	200	125
Vega	P6	92	92	65

Table 3: Prior sizes of the six pyramids.

The base sizes for Arcturus (P4) and Thuban (P5) were calculated mathematically, while their heights were best guesses. I selected Menkaure's height so that it matched Khufu's Kepler

Triangle design ($1 : \sqrt{\phi} : \phi$). However, Petrie [8] (section 81) suggested a height around 125¢, which I now accept as correct.

I determined Vega's (P6) base size mathematically, based on ratios in the skeleton blueprint. I was never really happy with that size.

Since the planetary correlation works so well for P2 as is, and P3 after adjusting the height from 126¢ to 125¢, I used the corresponding ratios to determine better heights for P4 and P5.

For P6, I knew the target ratio was the same as (Mercury/Jupiter), so I could get a target for the base sides (assuming square) and height, as well as knowing that these would be integers. I wrote a program to generate and check possibilities, which produced a list of 28 candidates, ranging from 133×133×105¢ (slope 57.57°) to 160×160×72¢ (slope 42.1°). I tried to find a combination that had a "sensible" design paradigm, and settled on 138×138×98¢, with a slope of 54.85°. Then height/(half base) is $98/(138/2) \approx 1.42 \approx \sqrt{2}$, giving us a design close to $1 : \sqrt{2} : \sqrt{3}$.

That gives us these revised sizes, and their volume as a percentage of Khufu.

<i>Giza / stellar name</i>	<i>P number</i>	<i>Base X ¢</i>	<i>Base Y ¢</i>	<i>Height ¢</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Khufu	P1	440	440	280	100.00
Khafre	P2	411	411	274	85.38
Menkaure	P3	201	195	125	9.04
Arcturus	P4	149	151	114	4.73
North Pole / Thuban	P5	193	200	119	8.47
Vega	P6	138	138	98	3.44

Table 4: Revised size and volumes of the pyramids, and as percentage of P1.

Comparing the ratios of planet diameters to Jupiter, and pyramid volumes to Khufu:

<i>Planet</i>	<i>Jupiter %</i>	<i>Khufu %</i>	<i>Pyramid</i>	<i>Px</i>
Jupiter	100.00	100.00	Khufu	P1
Saturn	84.30	85.38	Khafre	P2
Earth	8.92	9.04	Menkaure	P3
Venus	8.47	8.47	Thuban	P5
Mars	4.75	4.73	Arcturus	P4
Mercury	3.41	3.44	Vega	P6

Table 5: Planetary and pyramid ratios compared.

Fig. 4 shows this graphically.

Figure 4: Charting the percentages of Khufu and Jupiter.

There is excellent correlation between the two sets of ratios.

Menkaure works because I am using my proposed original base size of $201 \times 195\text{G}$, rather than the currently accepted $201 - 202\text{G}$ square.

The three smaller pyramids are impossible to verify. I had calculated the base sizes for the larger two previously in ZTM101, and now adjusted the heights to work. I found it curious that P5 and P3 were so similar (P3: $201 \times 195\text{G}$, P5: $193 \times 200\text{G}$). Now we know why.

P6 was calculated based on the target ratio and a reasonable design.

Khafre's base is related to Khufu's via the Douglas Triangle [9], and was built to a 3 : 4 : 5 design, which directly affects its proportion to Khufu.

4. The moons

Jupiter has 80 known moons, and some moonlets. The largest five are:

<i>Moon</i>	<i>Diameter km</i>	<i>Percentage of Jupiter</i>
Ganymede	5268.2	3.68
Callisto	4820.6	3.37
Io	3643.2	2.55
Europa	3121.6	2.18
Amalthea	167.0	0.12

The size drops off dramatically after the first four. We credit Galileo Galilei with discovering the four largest in 1609. Amalthea was only spotted in 1892.

Saturn has at least 83 moons. The sizes of the first two are:

<i>Moon</i>	<i>Diameter km</i>	<i>Percentage of Saturn</i>
Titan	5149.0	4.27
Rhea	1527.0	1.27

We see another dramatic drop in size, and hence visibility.

The Earth has one moon.

Khufu has (had) four satellite pyramids, all true pyramids, matching Jupiter's four main moons.

Khafre had one satellite pyramid, also a true pyramid, matching Saturn's main moon Titan.

Menkaure has three satellite pyramids. However, only the eastern one is a true pyramid, the other two are badly-built step mastabas. I propose that these two are later additions, and that originally, Menkaure had only one satellite pyramid, a true pyramid, matching Earth's sole moon.

Thus, we find correlation between the planets and their main moons, and the corresponding pyramids and their satellites.

Regarding the other three planets and their pyramids, with all physical evidence gone, we can only speculate.

5. Discussion

From the above, it is clear to me that the six pyramid sizes at Giza reflect the sizes of the planets relative to Jupiter. They are arranged from west to east in ascending size order, rather than in order of distance from the sun. That arrangement confused me. I tried to find a spot where the “sun” could go, without success. I wondered if I perhaps had Jupiter confused with Saturn. Including Saturn’s rings in the calculation did not help. So I accepted that maybe there were other reasons for the curious order.

The truth is, I was missing the huge hint they had already given. The correlation is between the 2D planet diameters, and the 3D pyramid volumes. In the same way, the arrangement works when you stop thinking in flat 2D plan mode, and think in 3D mode. If you treated the Giza plan as an edge-on view from a distant planet, where the astronomers are watching our planets transiting Sol just like we watch their planets transiting their star, then it makes sense.

I converted that edge-on view to a more familiar orbital views. What you see depends on where you are looking from. Fig. 5 shows the possible positions if looking from south of the plan. I rotated the image counter-clockwise to fit, so look at it from the right.

Figure 5: The planets matching Giza plan, from south of plan, rotated 90° counter-clockwise.

Fig. 6 shows the possible view for an observer to the east of the plan view.

Figure 6: The planets as at Giza, for viewer from east of plan.

In theory, with a suitable program and dataset, it should be possible to calculate dates from these arrangements. However, NASA's current dataset, DE441, only covers the years $-13,200$ to $+17,191$ [10], which will not match my expected date of circa 55.5k BCE.

Fig. 7 shows a size comparison from NASA: [11]

Figure 7: NASA image comparing the sizes of the planets.

Fig. 7 neatly illustrates why it would not have made sense to try and match the pyramids with the planets volumetrically. Earth's volume is about 0.07% of Jupiter's.

If we express Khufu's volume as a cube, it would have a side of 137.4 metres. A cube that is 0.07% of that volume would have a side 12.2 metres, making a rather unimpressive pyramid.

Although the matching is done on pyramid volume rather than base size, we can illustrate the arrangement. However, our brains do a poor job comparing 3D volumes to 2D diameters, so it "looks wrong." This may be because we look at the circle areas rather than the diameters, and can't convert proportional volume to linear scale in our heads.

Fig. 8 has a scale illustrating the problem:

Figure 8: Volume and diameter scale.

The cubes are drawn in the Douglas projection. [9]

If a cube has a side of 100, then one that is 50% of the volume has a side $\sqrt[3]{(100^3/2)} = 79.37$.

Fig. 9 shows the site plan, with the pyramids converted to cubes of the same volume, compared to Khufu’s volume. The sizes of the circles reflect the relative sizes of the planets.

Figure 9: The planets mapped to the pyramids.

With this good correlation, and evidence that the builders knew the main moons of both Jupiter and Saturn, we must conclude that they had optical instruments like telescopes. These were at least as powerful as that used by Christiaan Huygens to discover Titan in 1655.

The builders also had a reasonable idea of Earth’s size. They were also able to correctly convert the observed size of the planets to their actual size, which means they had a good idea of the distances as well, and the required mathematical skills.

Since we have no evidence of the 4th dynasty having such technology, we once again have to consider the possibility of a prior, technologically-advanced civilization that did.

Fig. 10 shows the labelled site map.

Figure 10: Pyramids with planetary names and symbols.

6. Acknowledgements

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